

Reduction of Chlorate, Bromate, and Iodate by Nitrous Acid

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Reduction of bromate, chlorate, and iodate by nitrite in presence of mineral acids has been studied potentiometrically. Chlorate consumes three moles nitrite under all the conditions investigated. Bromate consumes 2.5 moles or 3.0 moles, depending on the concentration of HCl or H₂SO₄ present; larger concentrations favour 2.5 moles. Iodate requires 5 moles. These results have been explained on the basis that nitrite ion is the main reducing agent in the cases of bromate and chlorate, whereas N₂O₃ is involved in the reduction of iodate. Several reaction mechanisms have been suggested, experimental conditions producing the difference in results observed.

Reduction of bromic acid to bromine by nitrous acid was first studied by Feit and Kubierschky¹ who also found that iodic acid could not be attacked in cold concentrated solution. Kurtenacker² examined the velocity of reduction of iodic acid and of bromic acid³ by nitrous acid; he found the velocity of reduction of the iodate to be directly proportional to the concentration of iodate, nitrite, and hydrogen ions and suggested the following mechanism:

the reaction being catalytically accelerated by the hypoiodous acid formed in the reaction. The reduction of bromate by nitrous acid, according to him, takes place as:

the velocity of the reaction being strongly accelerated by acetic acid.

Wesly *et al.*⁴ investigated the kinetics of oxidation of nitrous acid by chloric and bromic acids and found the reaction between chlorate and nitrous acid to be of second order, the velocity constant being proportional to H⁺ -ion concentration and alteration of Cl⁻-ion concentration producing no significant change in the velocity constant. The

1. *Chem. Ztg.*, 1891, 15, 351.

2. *Monatsh.*, 1914, 35, 407.

3. *Idem, ibid.*, p. 025.

4. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1934, 221, 173.

reaction with bromate is similarly unaffected by changing the Br^- -ion concentration, whence it is inferred that oxidation of Br^- ion to Br_2 plays no part in the overall mechanism.

The present work was undertaken to ascertain whether chlorates, bromates, and iodates could be determined by potentiometric titration with sodium nitrite as well as to gain insight into the nature of individual reactions that occur in varying concentrations of mineral acids. Bromate and iodate have been extensively used in potentiometric redox titrations⁵. Britton *et al.*⁶ have made potentiometric studies of the reduction of iodic acid and bromic acids by iodide.

EXPERIMENTAL

Titration of Bromate

(a). *In H_2SO_4 Solutions.*—Table I records the summary of the results. Some of the corresponding graphs are shown in Fig. 1.

TABLE I

V ml of 0.1M-KBrO₃+10 ml of x N-H₂SO₄+y ml of water in cell. M-NaNO₂ solution in the burette.

V.	x.	y.	Effective acid conc.	Inflection at.	Moles nitrite / Mole KBrO ₃	Curves.
5	0.1	5	0.05N	1.50	3.00	I
5	0.2	5	0.10	1.50	3.00	II
5	1.0	5	0.50	1.50	3.00	III
5	2.0	5	1.00	1.50	3.00	IV
3	4.0	7	2.00	0.90	3.00	VI
3	1.0	7	5.00	0.80	2.66	V
5	2.0	5	10.00	1.25	2.50	VII (not shown)

On the addition of nitrite, the solution immediately turned yellow due to liberation of bromine, the colour of which gradually deepened on addition of further nitrite. When sufficient nitrite was added to correspond to the point of inflection in the curves, the solution became colorless. Towards the beginning, stable values of E.M.F. were recorded within 10 to 15 minutes, but as titration progressed, more and more time was needed to record stable values; in the neighbourhood of the point of inflection, one hour or sometimes even more was required.

(b). *In HCl Solution.*—Titrations were performed only up to the acid concentration of 1N, beyond which the bromate started reacting with HCl itself with the liberation of enough chlorine, which could be identified by its colour, smell, and the reaction on starch iodide paper. Results are summarised in Table II.

5. Furman, *Ind Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1930, 2, 213; 1942, 14, 367; *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, 22, 33; 1951, 23, 21; 1954, 26, 84.

6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3877, 3879, 3887.

TABLE II

V ml of 0.1M-KBrO₃+10ml of x N-HCl+y ml of water in cell. M-NaNO₂ in burette.

V.	x.	y.	Effective acid conc.	Inflection at.	Moles nitrite / Mole KBrO ₃
5	0.1	5	0.05N	1.5	3.0
5	0.5	5	1.25	1.4	2.8
5	2.00	5	1.00	1.3	2.6

Other observations are similar to those in H₂SO₄ medium.

Titration of Chlorate

(a). In H₂SO₄ Solution.—The solution remained colorless during titration. Stable values of E.M.F. were recorded in nearly the same time as in the case of bromate, more time being needed in the neighbourhood of inflection. Results are summarised in Table III and in Fig. 2.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

TABLE III

x N-H₂SO₄ + 10 ml of 0.05M-KClO₃ in cell. M-NaNO₂ solution in burette.

x.	Effective acid conc.	Inflection at.	Moles nitrite / Mole KClO ₃	Curves.
0.2	0.1N	1.5	3.0	I
1.0	0.5	1.5	3.0	II
2.0	1.0	1.5	3.0	III
4.0	2.0	1.5	3.0	IV
10.0	5.0	1.5	3.0	V

(b). *In HCl Solution.*—The results obtained in HCl medium are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

0.05*M*-KClO₃ (10 ml) + *x N*-HCl (10 ml) in cell. *M*-NaNO₂ in burette.

<i>x</i> .	Effective acid conc.	Inflection at.	$\frac{\text{Moles nitrite}}{\text{Mole KClO}_3}$
0.1	0.05 <i>N</i>	1.5	3.0
1.0	0.50	1.5	3.0
4.0	2.00	1.4	2.9
6.0	3.00	1.4	2.8

Titration of Iodate

(a). *In H₂SO₄ Solution.*—Table V records a summary of the results. On addition of a few ml of nitrite, the solution became orange-red and remained so till the end of the titration. Qualitative tests showed presence of NO₂.

TABLE V

M/50-KIO₃ (10 ml) + *x N*-H₂SO₄ (10 ml) in cell. *M*-NaNO₂ in burette.

<i>x</i>	..	0.1	2.0	10.0
Inflection at	..	0.9	0.9	1.0
$\frac{\text{Moles nitrite}}{\text{Mole iodate}}$	..	4.5	4.5	5.0

In all cases, inflection corresponding to nearly 5 moles of nitrite per mole iodate was noticed in the titration curves. Stable readings on the potentiometer were recorded at the same time as in the case of bromate and nearly the same time was needed to complete a titration. The higher potentials set up in the first section of curves, when concentration of acid is increased, indicate the effect of greater H⁺-ion activity.

(b). *In HCl Solution.*—results are summarised in Table VI and in Fig. 3. The colour change and other observations were similar to those in H₂SO₄ solutions. Titrations were not performed with HCl concentration greater than *N*/4, as chlorine was then appreciably evolved.

TABLE VI

M/50-KIO₃ (10 ml) + *x N*-HCl (10 ml) in cell. *M*-NaNO₂ in burette.

<i>x</i> .	Effective acid conc.	Inflection at.	$\frac{\text{Moles nitrite}}{\text{Mole KIO}_3}$	Curves.
0.05	0.025	0.95	4.75	I
0.10	0.050	0.95	4.75	II
0.25	0.125	0.90	4.60	III

DISCUSSION

The titrations of bromate with nitrite have provided the most definite results as is clear from the graphs in Fig. 1. The notable features of these titrations are that in lower

concentrations of H_2SO_4 or HCl , an inflection is observed at three moles of nitrite added. When the concentrations of these acids are increased (towards $10\text{N-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ or 1N-HCl), the nitrite requirement falls to nearly 2.5 moles. The consumption of three moles nitrite may be explained as follows:

This reaction would require the mixture to remain colorless throughout the titrations. Actually, a yellow colour, characteristic of bromine, developed with the first few drops of nitrite and persisted till towards the end of the titration. A little before the inflection was observed, it started fading and vanished completely at the inflection point. Reaction (a) shows that after the commencement of the titration, both bromate and bromide ions are present in an acid mixture so that free bromine must appear in the mixture.

Comparing reactions (a) and (b), we find that if we start with 1 mole bromate and leave $1/6$ mole unconsumed, there would be $5/6$ mole of Br produced. These will react as at (b) and all the original bromine in bromate will appear as free bromine. Reaction (b) does not require any nitrite. The total nitrite requirement in (a) will be $3 \times 5/6$ mole or 2.5 moles. If conditions are favourable, the liberated bromine may take up half mole more of nitrite and an equivalent quantity of bromide ions may be generated.

Since H^+ ions are required in (b), the rate of this reaction is likely to be suppressed in mixtures containing dilute H_2SO_4 or HCl . In fact, when the mineral acid concentration was low, the yellow colour initially developed was more feeble than in more concentrated solutions. This

FIG. 3

indicates that two paths are open for the reduction of bromate to bromide, either directly through (a) or through (a), (b), and (c).

These experiments show that there are reasonable conditions under which pure HBr is formed from bromate. We presume that under these conditions it may be possible for

H_2SO_4 to displace HBr from a bromide without liberation of bromine. It cannot be stated without further experiments whether a dilute solution of HBr may be distilled from one such mixture without contamination with bromine. Further pursuit of these titrations at higher temperatures will be of much interest.

The titration graphs obtained with chlorate are not so steep nor so neat, yet the final inflections are quite definite. In all sulphuric acid concentrations one finds that 3 moles of nitrite are consumed. It is well known that the chlorate-chloride analogue of (b) is slow. The only assertive reaction left is the analogue of (a) and quite rightly 3 moles of nitrite are consumed (Table III). In a high concentration of HCl (Table IV), the large excess of chloride ions accelerates (b) to some extent and the nitrite requirement falls to 2.8 in 3*N*-HCl.

We have reported in an earlier paper⁷ that when nitrite is added to HCl in presence of air, the nitrite requirement is much larger than that required for displacement of nitrous acid, equivalent to the HCl present. The discrepancy was about 45% in 0.09*N*-HCl but decreased to about 25% in 2*N*-HCl. We explained this result on the basis that aerial oxidation of the liberated nitrous acid took place, the overall reaction being

If such an oxidation asserted itself in the titration described above, one should note serious departures from the neat molar ratios. The reason for not observing such departures is that the reaction (a) and its analogue for chlorate are much faster than the aerial oxidation of nitrous acid. Bromate and chlorate serve the same purpose as potassium iodide or urea did in the earlier paper⁷.

The analogue of (a) for KIO_3 does not seem to be such a fast reaction. Tables V and VI show that nitrite requirement of one mole of iodate is 4.5 moles at low H_2SO_4 or HCl concentrations, but increases to 5.0 when H_2SO_4 concentration tends towards 5*N*. It may seem therefore that the part of nitrite which escapes oxidation by the iodate is perhaps oxidised by the atmospheric oxygen. Our previous experience would, however, require that atmospheric oxidation should be less in higher concentrations of mineral acid, contrary to the present observation. Another curious fact is that the nitrite requirement is almost doubled from 2.5 to 5.0. A reference to Table II(c) in the above cited paper will show that a wider variation in nitrite consumption should be expected as the mineral acid concentration is changed.

Apparently iodate, being a less powerful oxidising agent, fails to oxidise NO_2^- to NO_3^- , *i.e.* from N (III) to N (v). If with iodate the oxidation is from N (III) to N (IV), the nitrite requirement will be doubled. When the end product is iodine, the nitrite requirement should be 2×2.5 or 5.0, the figure we have observed most frequently in these titrations with iodate. At least in the case of HCl mixture, the fall of nitrite requirement at higher concentration of HCl is correctly explained (analogue of eq. b). Both H_2SO_4 and HCl mixtures, however, show some anomalies as the acid concentration changes.

Equations (a) and (b) may be rewritten in this reduction as:

The net reaction then is

showing clearly that one mole of iodate will react with 2.5 moles of N_2O_3 = 5.0 moles of nitrite, producing one mole I_2 . The particle N_2O_3 has been also made use of by earlier workers to explain oxidation-reduction reactions; for example, Bunton *et al.*¹⁰ have used it for explaining the oxidation of ascorbic acid by nitrite solutions.

Seemingly, in any reasonable concentration of HCl or H_2SO_4 , there are two paths for reduction of KIO_3 , either by the nitrite ion (reaction a) or by N_2O_3 (reaction a'). Perhaps the same is true of the reduction of chlorate and bromate; only it is a question of relative speeds of reactions (a) and (a') in any particular reduction, which will determine the actual nitrite requirement. The figures around 4.5 perhaps indicate that the analogue of reaction (a) is not negligible in some of the reductions of iodate, noted above.

Comparing once again the reactions of chlorate, bromate, and iodate according to (a), the reaction appears to be faster for chlorate, less so for bromate, and quite slow for iodate. The reduction to chloride therefore takes place almost entirely by route (a), whereas bromate is reduced to bromide only partially by (a), the larger portion taking the route (a) → (b) → (c). In the case of iodate, almost all the reduction is through (a'). Conditions exist under which reaction (c) may be totally suppressed in the reduction of bromate.

To find full support for these ideas, kinetic measurements will be necessary, but perhaps some justification may be obtained by measurements of oxidation potentials of the various couples involved under conditions approximating those of the present experiments.

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